

1-TOM, 12-SON
THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN DETERMINING A
PERSON'S LIFE AND ITS IMPACT ON THE FUTURE

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

The Faculty of Psychology, the department of Foreign languages
Philology and foreign languages

Scientific advisor: Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi
nafisateshaboyeva@jbnuu.uz

Student of group 401-22: Eshkobilova Farangiz Gayrat qizi

Annotation: This article deals with what is motivation (you can learn external motivation and internal motivation as well as some techniques with a bit more power), the importance of motivation, why do we need a motivation in our life (you will witness the real-life experience, its benefit and result in my future, as well as, some quotes said by celebrities). It is no secret that, motivation is an integral part of our life that can lead us to a large number of achievements. It also opens every door easily along the way when we have a lot on our mind.

Key words: Self-confidence, self-motivation, external standards, invoke the passion, labors of love, drive innovation, deeper meaning in one's life, hierarchy of needs.

As everybody knows, motivation plays the most important role to achieve a lot of achievements in our life, as somebody motivates us, the probability of realization of our goals increases even more. Besides, we have a passion to do everything and we keep striving to acquire it. Even famous and great people were motivated by someone or something to achieve today's results and achievements. Without motivation, it is difficult to imagine our tomorrow. In a word, motivation increases a person's self-confidence. As you have likely already guessed, self-motivation is an important concept. While pleasing others and meeting external standards can certainly motivate us to get things done, such efforts are not exactly labors of love. In other words, doing things because, we feel we have to do them or to gain some external reward, is enough in many cases, but it does not invoke the passion needed to drive innovation and excellence. It is fine to use external sources to motivate you some areas, but external motivation is less likely to leave you feeling personally fulfilled and finding deeper meaning in your life. Not only do we generally do better work when we are doing what we want to be doing [1, 23]. "Your imperfections make you beautiful, they make you who you are, so just be yourself, love yourself for who you are and

1-TOM, 12-SON

just keep going". [2]. The idea belongs to Demi Lovato. I see eye to eye with this idea. For the reason that, when a person believes himself or herself and motivate, they can reach to great heights. The most important thing is nit to stop moving. We can cite J. Rowling's life as an example on this condition. "J. K. Rowling had just gotten a divorce, was on government aid, and could barely afford to feed her baby in 1994, just three years before the first Harry Potter book, "Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" was published. When she was shopping it out, she was so poor, she could not afford a computer or even the cost of photocopying the 90 000-word novel, so she manually types out each version to send to publishers and she did not give up trying and believed herself. So, it was rejected dozens of times, until finally Bloomsburry, a small London publisher gave it a second chance after the CEO's eight year-old daughter feel in love with it".[3]. As you can see, self-motivation is all about where your drive comes from; if your motivation comes from within and pushes you to achieve for your own personal reasons. It can be considered self-motivation.

If you need techniques with a bit more power you can try these:

- set wisely chosen and deeply personal goals that you are excited about working toward;
- schedule rewards for yourself when you accomplish your goals (or when you make steps toward your goals);
- visualize yourself achieving and fulfilling these goals;
- create a vision board with your goals, aims and dreams in mind, and poat it somewhere you will see it often;
- pay attention to your "hierarchy of needs" (Abraham Maslov) and ensure you are meeting your lower-level needs(including physiological needs like food and sleep, safety needs, social needs and esteem needs);
- consider using Neuro-Linguistic Programming(NLP), the study linking neurology, language, and programming to understand human experience and motivation;
- envision what could happen when you reach your goals, as well as, what could happen when you fail to reach your goals;
- incorporate things you are interested in and engage your curiosity when setting and working toward your goals;
- make a commitment to someone or something to ensure your future self will find it difficult to change plans or put things of (Muller 2012). [4, 26].

1-TOM, 12-SON

If you try to do these techniques, you can enjoy living, and you can get even the greatest achievements.

WHY DO WE NEED A MOTIVATION IN OUR LIFE?

It goes without saying, motivation helps us to build strength and complete any task or work. It teaches us not to give up on our dreams even during difficult times and study focused and committed to fulfill our dreams or complete tasks or work. Different people are motivated by different things and at different times in their lives.

There are 2 types of motivation: external motivation and internal motivation.

- External motivation: Reward: We do things, because it gives us respect, recognition, opportunities to grow further, money or power.
- Internal motivation: Love: We do things, because they make us happy, healthy and feel good.

Both of them are very beneficial for us as they teach us to be and insistent. Even I was motivated and challenged by external motivation. To tell the truth, after completing my tenth class, I was in a lot of confusion and I could not make a choice between studying in my hometown or in another place and I was in an impossible dilemma. So yes, from my childhood till now, a lot of decisions were taken by my parents and we know that a right decision can do wonders, whereas a bad decision can cost you a fortune. Hence, I had to make a careful decision. Thus, I thought it would be good for me if I pursue my higher studies in another place. On the other hand, studying in a host town requires many funds and we had many financial problems at that time. Therefore, I was not able to make any decision about my future, and after some days, I started feeling irritated. One day, I decided to talk to all my family members regarding my frustration. Fortunately, my teacher, Mr. Navruz Toshmatov explained me the benefits of studying in another place. He also pointed out that the course I want to pursue will be better suited if I study in a coaching center called "Intelligent" which was headquartered by him. He also told me not to worry about the funds as he would aid me with this problem. My parents agreed instantly and then my teacher advised me to go for the IELTS test. This decision cleared the air and confusion on my mind. As a result, now, I am really focused, and I have planned to apply in a University in a foreign country.

As you all guess, due to the motivation of my teacher, my whole studies is hanging in a balance, in present day. What comes to my surprise that, although I did not consider myself a necessary person for the society, he always believes that, one day I would be a great person in my field in the future. With the help of my teacher, I

1-TOM, 12-SON

acquired today's degree. Therefore, I wish, he would proud of me and I could justify his confidence!!! Always remember one thing, on the road to success, there is only another person who is standing behind you maybe not coming on the forefront but behind of you, waiting for you and supporting you. Never lose that person. Never... My teacher was such a person, my external motivator!

As you yourself have witnessed, motivation is the key of success. The most important thing is not to give up acting and believing yourself. According to Ryan Gosling's opinion, "It is word-formation important not to limit yourself. You can do whatever you really love to do, no matter what it is".

In conclusion, taking everything into the consideration, without motivation, we can not imagine our life as it serves as an important support that determines the future of every person. It is the main source that motivates a person who when he or she is in a difficult situation and arouses interest in living. It is no secret that motivation awakens in a person the desire to achieve great things. What is required of you is to never give up and believe that you can so what you set your mind to. Here are motivational quotes from many famous people. For instance; "Never worry about bad press. All that matters is if they spell your name right". (Kate Hudson). "It is the choice. You have to wake up everyday and say, there is no reason today can not be the best day of my life". (Blake Lively).

Motivation is like a poet's angel of inspiration that helps him in times of need. Firstly, we should be able to be thankful for our existence and to live in this life. We have parents and love ones who care for us. Thank goodness, we can do everything we can. We know that there are many disabled people around us, but they are also living with hope, intentions, aims, dreams and also motivation from somewhere. We should follow their examples. In fact, our existence in this life is the greatest motivation for us!

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. "Motivation: Definition, Types, Theories, and How to Find It" - Verywell Mind. Link: www.verywellmind.com
2. "How Thinking About the Future Makes Life More Meaningful" - Greater Good Magazine, Berkeley.edu. Link: greatergood.berkeley.edu
3. "The Vital Importance and Benefits of Motivation" - PositivePsychology.com. Link: positivepsychology.com
4. "The Power of Future Thinking for Healthy Living" - Verywell Mind. Link: www.verywellmind.co

1-TOM, 12-SON

5. Teshaboyeva, N., & Mamayoqubova, S. (2020). COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 409-414).

6. Teshaboyeva, N. (2020). LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY, ITS STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE NEW PERSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 415-420).

7. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2019). TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERATURE IN TESL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. In СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ (pp. 82-84).

8. Маърипов Д. Psychological value of the novels by agatha christie //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 630-632.

9. Teshaboyeva, N. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM IN PRESENT DAY. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 5(5).

10. Teshaboyeva, N. (2023). THE MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 5(5).

11. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2023, November). Adjective word group and its types. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 59-61).

12. Teshaboyeva, N. Z. (2023, November). Modifications of Consonants in Connected speech. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 7-9).

13. Nafisa, T., & Marina, S. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN TESL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 465-469.

14. Ibrohimovna, X. M. (2023). The Importance of Methods in Language Teaching Process. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 2(1), 20-23.

15. Хидирова, Д., & Тешабоева, Н. (2022). Pedagogical conditions for the development of the healthy thinking in students. Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar, 1(1), 120-122.

1-TOM, 12-SON

16. Ma'ripov J. Antroposentrizm–tilshunoslikning zamonaviy yonalishi sifatida //Иновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 28. – С. 62-68.

17. Rakhmankulovna A. S. PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETITION IN YOUNG PEOPLE OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2023. – С. 18-20.

18. Rakhmankulovna A. S. THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING AND THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 09. – С. 58-62.

